

BEYOND TECH: RISING AWARENESS FOR THE OPEN SEARCH FOUNDATION

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Abstract

The Open Search Foundation (OSF) was officially founded in September 2018. It was the end of a first iterative process in order to establish a movement of people and organizations that work together to create the foundations for independent, free and self-determined access to information on the Internet. The center of the activities of the OSF in this time was the so called Tech Group that was established in May 2018. Together with experts from European computer centers and research institutions, the focus was on conducting decentralized indexing experiments and advanced concepts. In addition, first supporters of the Open Search movement were gained from the private and public sectors [1].

But the work of the OSF must and will go beyond the technical aspects, particularly since the Non-Profit (NP) entered phase 2 in its development after the official foundation in September 2018. Therefore, a set of additional working groups were initialized. One important working group is the Awareness working group. According to the vision of the OSF it is not only the objective to ensure greater diversity in the European search engine landscape and to develop the basis for indexes that are available to citizens according to transparent criteria. Another important aspect of the vision of the OSF is to educate the people about the existing problem of network monopolies, particularly with regard to the search infrastructure [2]. The discussions in the last years in promoting the idea of the OSF demonstrated the big necessity to do so, since most people are not aware of the existing monopoly-problem. In addition, the ever-advancing digitization of our daily life and the increasing use of Internet technologies in all spheres of our societies imply that we need to sharpen the awareness of how the OSF wants to deploy and govern the use of these technologies [3]. Hence, there is a huge need for the OSF to increase its communication activities in order to reach its public welfare objectives and to address the relevant target groups.

Such tailor-made communication is becoming increasingly relevant for non-profit organizations (NPOs) like the OSF. In this context, NPOs in general have a high global reputation due to their non-profit character. Big names such as Greenpeace, Doctors without Borders or Amnesty International are an eye catcher for the public. Smaller NPOs, or those that are just starting up like the OSF, have to fight for recognition and financial resources. More and more organizations are competing for fewer and fewer

funding resources. These are needed to generate the necessary awareness of the concerns of the respective NPO. From this aspect, however, a seemingly contradictory problem arises. Fundraising, attention and awareness are closely intertwined and mutually dependent (Hiemer 2020, p. 1). On the one hand, it requires financial means to generate attention and awareness, which is why donations are needed. On the other hand a non-profit organization like the OSF needs donations to get attention and awareness in order to set up the required tailor-made communication approach.

So, how did other NPOs and particularly NPO start-ups deal with this problem in the past? Since there are only a few sources with regard to this issue, an in-depth primary qualitative research was set up. Within the qualitative survey, guideline-based interviews with experts and actors from the NP sector were used to identify special features of NP communication in the start-up phase and to solve the contradictory problem. The results demonstrated that the necessary focal points in the beginning of the communication approach must be the set-up of image and attention as well as the building of a group of supporters. Awareness then results from attention. Fundraising is only successful after image, attention and awareness have been generated. Based on the findings, an individual concept was created for the OSF. It follows the typical phases of analysis, strategy and implementation and finally gives recommendations for its application. In this paper an example of the communication work package for the main target group “recipients/users” is presented to give first insights into the communication work planned by the Open Search Foundation.

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1 Network Monopolies as Challenges in the Search Engine Market - Especially for Europe

1.1 The Need for an Independent Search Index for Europe

Information is certainly one of the most important resources in this world in the 21st century. And where can you find the most information? On the Internet. And: Today, it is hard to imagine the Internet without search engines. 98% of web entries are made via a search engine. Google alone serves over 2,000,000,000 search queries per year [1]. While in the 1990s the Internet was still largely organized via Internet addresses, so-called domains, it is now unusual to enter a domain in its entirety. The user even uses search engines, although he knows the name (and thus also the domain of the address).

The connection between search engine and search index

At this point, a short excursion is made in order to better understand the following explanations. It is about the connection of search engines and the necessary search index as a basis.

The function of a search engine can be described simply: search engines search the WWW or more correctly an image of the WWW and filter the Internet according to a certain algorithm. This image is called search engine index (or search index or web index). A web index is therefore the basis for search engines - however, it is not the same, it just enables us to search the Internet quicker.

The search index is a kind of card file, a cartography of the Internet: a directory of all information and documents accessible via the Internet. Search engines access an index to produce results quickly and based on algorithms. Without this index, a search engine would have to search the entire Web with its billions of pages for every query - and that would take a lot of time. Whether and how a piece of information can be found on the Internet is decided in the search index even before the search engine starts its work. Seen in this light, a search index is the heart of a search engine.

What influence do search engines have on our memory?

As described above, we have become accustomed to searching for everything. The indexing of the Internet by the human brain has become too cumbersome for us and so the search engine is used for everything. A study from the USA by Sparrow, Liu and Wegner from 2011 proves that the frequent use of search engines influences and changes our memory. As soon as a person assumes that he or she can quickly retrieve a piece of information using a search engine, the brain no longer stores this information. Thus, the brain unlearns to learn [2, pp. 776-778]. Search engines have thus become our collective memory aid. In this respect, it is even more relevant today than it was twenty

years ago what results the search engines give us. This is because studies have also shown that we humans believe that if something is displayed in the upper regions of the results lists by one of the popular search engines, then it must be true [3].

What are network monopolies and are they dangerous?

This connection seems even more important because there are only a handful of search indexes of significance in the world: Baidu (China), Yandex (Russia), Bing and Google (both USA). They are either commercially oriented or state-controlled. None of them is based in Europe.

Google has a global market share of 92 percent [4]. In Europe, this market share is even higher [5]. In the eastern world, Baidu, the search engine controlled by the Chinese state, is the clear market leader. In both cases, we speak of network monopolies. These arise due to the so-called network effect. The central thesis of the theory states: In every network, the benefit for all participants increases disproportionately when new participants join [6, pp. 197-198].

As a consequence, customers usually choose the provider with the largest network among all providers. And this tendency has also proven true with regard to search engines in the last decade. The search engine landscape has become a "The-Winner-Takes-It-All" market.

If search engines including their indexes are our collective memory support, isn't it dangerous if we leave this to just one company? Is it not questionable if the information provided by search engine operators contributes to the formation of public opinion? Is such a wealth of power in the hands of a few - commercial or state-controlled - companies not an invitation to abuse and manipulation?

These questions must be asked, especially since these major search engines operate neither openly, transparently nor neutrally. The more users a search engine binds to itself, the higher its influence within the search engine optimization and thus also the influence on the results. This is shown above all by the fact that 80 percent of clicks lead to the same 10,000 domains [3, p. 2]. Only the first hits of the result lists are usually considered important [7, p. 21]. The infrastructures of the search engines are based on non-transparent filtering, location, and personalization algorithms, which bring the mass of content into a "meaningful" ranking using also the knowledge about previous searches. Each user thus receives different search engine result pages based on his or her individual interests. Distortions in the neutrality of the search results arise. This results in filter bubbles, selective perceptions and opinions, and restricted access to information [8, pp. 3-4].

Aren't these concerns exaggerated?

Many people, when confronted with such contexts, think that the concerns described are exaggerated. After all, the search engines deliver good results. Why should one worry about this? In this respect, it is worth taking a look at the

two "search engine worlds". Thereby it becomes apparent that both existing models - to put it mildly - are not optimal...

In the Western world, we have the dominance of a market-driven search engine, Google. The purely market-driven solution in terms of a laissez-faire mentality led to the dominance due to the described network effect. Now, first of all, the market-driven development as such is not a mistake. But the question still arises whether such a network monopoly can be healthy for a market? Can such a search engine of a commercial group with profit-oriented goals, which is financed by advertising, be neutral? In this context there is an interesting quote on this question, which reads:

"For this type of reason and historical experience with other media we expect that advertising funded search engines will be inherently biased towards the advertisers and away from the needs of the consumers".

In other words: a search engine that is financed by advertising delivers manipulated results. The question that arises now is: Who said that? The answer may be astonishing, but it has been confirmed: It was Larry Page and Sergey Brin, the two founders of Google [9].

At this point, we can pick up the ball from above: Google is a monopolist that determines our view of the world, says information scientist Dirk Lewandowski. His research shows: What is at the top of Google search results will be recognized, what is not at the top will not be recognized. Users believe: if something is at number one on Google, it must be right [Lewandowski quoted in 10, p. 21].

And all of this is based on non-transparent search indexes and algorithms, a lack of neutrality, and a supposed focus on advertisers. Added to this is another danger: a network monopoly like Google can abuse its power, manipulate and/or change the rules at any time. To name just three of many cases: The case with Huawei in 2019, for example, showed that Google temporarily stopped providing its Android operating system, at the insistence of President Trump [11]. And it is no coincidence that since 2017, more than 8 billion Euros in fines have been imposed on Google by the EU alone [12]. Even the US government recently accused Google of unfair competition in a lawsuit [13]. Evidence enough that Google has the means to manipulate and has already done so several times.

In this respect, one can ask whether a state-operated search engine is better. This brings us to the second alternative: As mentioned, there is a system controlled by an authoritarian state power in the East of the world: Baidu from China. We think that it is clear to everyone that this cannot be good and that the search engine is a huge data octopus that observes the behavior of the population in China. The data is even used to divide the population into

social classes, according to which people receive access or no access to certain services [14].

No existing approach is optimal - time to act

The Internet has become so successful because it is open. We can all surf it, research it, communicate with it and develop it further. This openness is - as shown - in danger and in many areas already no longer given. Among other things, the concentration on a few powerful search engines is endangering the freedom of the Internet.

If we now look at the role of Europe in this search engine market, we will find only marginal players. There are virtually no serious search engines with their own search index that are based in Europe. Europe plays practically no role in connection with digitization in general and Internet search in particular. Europe's dependence on a search engine monopoly also means a social and political risk. After all, business, education, research and culture need diversity in order to thrive - diversity is needed in the digital space as well.

1.2 The Basic Conceptual Idea of OSF: The Integrated Solution Approach

The freedom of the Internet is important for all of us. Searching the Internet is a free, public good; it belongs to all of us. Looking at the situation and the problems outlined in chapter 1.1, the Open Search Foundation (OSF) was founded as a charitable non-profit organization (NPO) in September 2018.

The basic conceptual idea is based on an integrated solution approach that has already been applied in other projects. First, the approach is similar to the development of the European GALILEO satellite navigation system for orientation and navigation in the physical world. Similar to the GALILEO project, the OSF also wants to leach the Internet search from private monopolies. For this purpose, insights from the developments of open operating systems as in Linux as well as public moderation as in Wikipedia will be used. Finally, following the approach of Lewandowski [3, p. 3], the infrastructural part of the search engine (the index) shall be separated from the operational part (the search engine). This allows a variety of services like search engines or other services such as cloud services or IoT, to be operated on a common infrastructure.

The technical foundation is derived from these aspects.

Three pillars form the technical foundation

1) Cooperative, distributed computing and hosting

A European web index and the associated search infrastructure can be established in Europe with manageable effort and, relative to its importance, very low costs. For the Open Search project, data centers in Europe make their free computing, storage and network capacities available. Together, they index the Web to create an open search index

and keep it up-to-date. This shared, decentralized computing and hosting eliminates the need for completely new server farms – which is better for the environment and at lower costs at the same time. The idea is to use the power of the many to accomplish the task in a financially viable and relatively short-term framework. It is important to accept that the creation and maintenance of this search infrastructure will only be possible as a common approach and without commercial interests. The approach is therefore: together and not commercially.

The fact that such decentralized indexing works is demonstrated by the OSF's technical experiments with experts from the European data centers and research institutions already involved. Several million .de domains have already been indexed on a test basis [15].

2) Open source principles and algorithms

Similar to the open-source operating system Linux, the development and expansion of the Internet search infrastructure will be based on open-source principles and algorithms. Various communities are working to build and enhance the system, for example in the areas of crawling, indexing, web search, and IT security.

Non-technical disciplines such as ethics and law are also involved in the development. Of course, a balance must be found between openness and security of the system. However, the open source principles ensure that the functioning of the overall system is traceable and transparent.

3) Public, transparent and unbiased moderation

Every search index must be thematically, linguistically, structurally and content-wise designed and maintained. This task is of particular importance in Internet search: even before a search algorithm can begin its work, the database and search index determine whether and how information, a website or a topic can be found on the Internet at all.

This highly responsible task of maintenance must not be left to chance, to a de facto single algorithm, or to possibly one-sided commercial or political interests. Rather, maintenance must be organized on the basis of transparent rules, with public auditing processes and with the participation of experts as objectively as possible and in a legally unobjectionable manner.

This very important part of building and maintaining the search infrastructure is called "public moderation." In addition to a wide variety of expert groups, libraries and lawyers, the public is also involved in order to ensure "democratic" verifiability and the integrity of the content and structures. This also involves economic, ethical and legal issues that must be considered.

Further building blocks of the integrated solution approach

OSF wants to ensure more diversity in the Internet search landscape. But just developing technical solutions is not enough. What many see as a disadvantage that Europe was so far out of the loop in digitization, can now become an advantage. Aspects that came up short in the development of other search indexes and engines are now becoming integral parts. Analogous to the elements of the OSF vision (see chapter 3), other building blocks are included in the basic conceptual idea of the OSF approach. And this has already been partly indicated in the context of the explanations of the technical approach. On the one hand, it is about legal and ethical aspects in the context of Internet search. On the other hand, there is the fact that the "business model" must not be based on individual entrepreneurial or governmental objectives, but must be sustainable and committed to the common good.

The success of such an approach can only be achieved through good and comprehensive communication. That is why another important component of the Open Search Foundation's concept is to raise people's awareness of the problem and to enhance digital competence. Because only those who understand the problem have the basis to change their behavior.

As a starting point, the question arose what learnings other NPOs were able to gather in the course of their start-up communications.

2 Analysis of start-up communication by NPOs

2.1 Literature review and derivation of further research needs

As part of OSF's start-up work since September 2018, a large number of conversations have been held. Partly to make people aware of the issues, partly to gain the necessary supporters. The following problems emerged:

- People, in the private sector as well as in organizations, are not aware that such a problem exists. It also shows that it is a very complex problem that is not easy to explain.
- In case someone is aware of the problem, many do not know how to deal with it. Many are also just too comfortable to change their behavior.
- In politics and the media, network monopolies are viewed more critically these days - but the issue of Internet search is usually left out.
- If OSF succeeds in creating the best search solution together with other competitors, too few people know about it! There is a lack of brand awareness.

Consequently, tailored communication with the relevant target groups is increasingly playing a key role, even for an NPO start-up like the OSF. The associated goals of "raising awareness of this issue" and "increasing the profile of

OSF" should also help to collect the necessary funds in the context of fundraising. However, this puts an NPO start-up like OSF in direct competition with large, already established organizations such as Greenpeace or Doctors without Borders. Smaller NPOs or those just starting out, like the OSF, have to fight for recognition and funding.

The question thus arises as to how other NPOs and especially NPO start-ups have dealt with similar problems in the past? What specifics are there to consider with regard to external communication? A comprehensive literature review provided initial insights into these questions in general [16, pp. 19-25, for a detailed discussion), but mostly not specifically with regard to the start-up phase. Most aspects were not surprising at all (see Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Specifics of communication of non-profit organizations [Source: Based on 16, p. 25 and the literature research conducted].

Nevertheless, the findings are initially helpful as confirmation of things that had already been started on the OSF side. For example, the fact that communication is given a higher priority in the NP sector than in the profit sector, as it often represents the performance itself and thus the only relationship between NPOs and their stakeholders [17, pp. 91-92].

An important statement - although not with specific reference to NPOs - was provided by Bittner-Fessler and Häfelinger [18, p. 14], according to which the start-up phase is primarily about attention, awareness, acceptance, and funding. From this, a seemingly "contradictory problem" can be derived, which was also already known on the OSF side: Fundraising, attention and awareness are closely intertwined and mutually dependent: on the one hand, financial resources (primarily via donations) are needed to generate attention and awareness. On the other hand, a non-profit organization like the OSF needs donations to generate attention and awareness [16, p. 1]. Since there were virtually no useful references in the literature regarding the question, of how to resolve this as an NPO in the start-up phase (with the exception of Urselmann's book about fundraising for NPOs [19]), the identified research gap had to be closed with a qualitative primary study.

2.2 NP start-up communication from the expert's point of view

Due to the fact that, as described in chapter 2.1, no literature could be found particularly with regard to the seemingly "contradictory problem" mentioned there, seven guided interviews with experts from the NP sector were conducted as part of a qualitative primary survey. The aim was also to identify additional insights into the special features of NP communication in the start-up phase.

With regard to the method of the qualitative study conducted, the sequence of steps shown in Fig. 2 was followed, the content of which is based on the procedures of Gläser and Laudel [20; with regard to steps 1 to 4] as well as Mayring [21] and Kuckartz [22; with regard to steps 5 and 6]. Further information on the individual steps can also be found in Fig. 2. Details can be found in [16, pp. 30-37].

1. Research questions	2. Choice of method	3. Choice of experts	4. Conducting interviews	5. Transcription and data interpretation	6. Data analysis and evaluation
What are the particularities of the start-up phase of a non-profit organization with regard to its external communication? How can the seemingly contradictory problem between recognition, awareness and funding be solved?	Guideline-based expert interviews Guideline was set up on basis of the findings from literature research, particularly with regard to the research gaps identified.	A set of 45 experts from NPOs (founders, board members, company spokesman and / or fundraisers) was derived from research 7 experts gave a positive feedback (reduced number due to COVID-19 and confidentiality reasons)	Telephone interviews in winter 2020/21 Duration between 30 to 60 minutes Recording of telephone interviews	Transcription and data preparation followed the well proven principles of Mayring (2015)	Data analysis based on the well proven content structured content analysis of Kuckartz (2018) Use of a deductive approach using also the MaxQDA software program

Fig. 2: Procedure in the context of the qualitative expert interviews [Source: 16, p. 30].

The results regarding the specifics of NPO communication in the start-up phase can be briefly summarized as follows [16, pp: 38-57 for details]:

- The results of the data analysis provide diverse and, in some cases, highly varying views of the experts on the start-up communication of NPOs.
- General statements on specific characteristics can hardly be found.
- Communication and measures depend on the NPO's field of activity, its positioning, goals, topics and target groups. NPOs are not comparable with each other, individual solutions have to be found.
- There are no real differences or special features between start-up communication and the communication of longer existing NPOs. Initial communication differs only insignificantly from NP communication that has already existed for several years.

By contrast, the findings from the expert interviews provide considerably more clues with regard to the above-mentioned "seemingly contradictory problem". According to the experts, the necessary focus at the beginning of the communications approach must be on building image and attention. Communication must also initially focus on building a supporter base. Any action must be based on

generating a contact or address and focused on retention of the contact. Awareness then results from attention.

Fundraising does not play a role in the initial communication - it only makes sense in a later phase, when supporters have been generated and image, attention and also a certain level of awareness have been built up.

3 Development of a specific communication approach for the OSF

Perhaps it was presumptuous in the context of the literature review and the qualitative expert interviews to get more concrete and clearer indications of how NPO start-ups should generally design their communication. In the end, what is true for most companies - NPO or not - is that it takes an individual approach. Nevertheless, the results of the research approach provided some confirmation and additionally directional approaches for the (further) development of the communication approach for the OSF.

The concept developed on the basis of these findings follows the typical phases of analysis, strategy and implementation (in detail following the general conceptual framework of Schmidbauer and Jorzik [23, pp. 68, 180, 290]) and finally gives recommendations for its application. But it would be too extensive to be presented in this paper, which is why only the basic pillars are discussed here. These are the vision, the mission as starting points, the definition of the "target groups" and the goals as well as an overview of the work packages for one of the main target groups.

Vision of the OSF

The vision first developed in the run-up to the study described in chapter 2 was further developed on the basis of the findings. In addition to the claim "Together for a better net," the basis is the formula "One open search index, many new search engines."

It also states: Pluralism of opinion and diversity of information are important cornerstones of democracy. Free orientation and self-determined access to information on the Internet must be a public right. Just as land and street maps and cadastral information are public goods today and accessible to people free of charge, the Internet must also be mapped openly in a search index. The Open Search Foundation is laying the foundation for open, transparent, and independent Internet search in Europe and beyond - making orientation on the web a public, transparent, and freely available good. [24, p. 12].

Mission of the OSF

To answer the question of how to achieve the vision, OSF relies on research and education so that everyone as a society can take advantage of a transparent and diverse search on the Internet. And: What we cannot do as individuals, we must do together! We want to develop the open search index in cooperation with data centers, science,

companies and civil society. Many people and organizations are working decentrally but together on the infrastructure for the Internet search of the next generation [24, p. 14).

Target groups

Part of OSF's vision (further elaborated than here) is to shape an awareness of problems among the population and to develop people's attitudes and behavior on the Internet in the direction of more diversity. In general, these are Internet users in Europe who use search engines. In addition, the open search index also provides the basis for business, research and industry in Europe to set up new business models. They are referred to as "*recipients*" (in the sense of service recipients) or "*users*" and form the main target group.

The work of OSF is based on the cooperative idea (see above "Together for a better net"). The forward-looking idea is dependent on every support. Every citizen of the EU is invited to join in thinking, shaping, sensitizing, convincing and persuading his or her own organization to participate in this project or to support the Open Search movement through financial means. This group of "*supporters*" may be partly identical to the target group of recipients in terms of the individuals and institutions involved. However, since a different goal is being pursued here, the group must be approached with different means and content.

Intermediaries were defined as the third and final target group. Intermediaries are central to reaching the various stakeholder groups that are widely dispersed throughout Europe. Since there is still little budget for the activities (at least currently), they are urgently needed as message spreaders. These can be representatives of the press in general, but also supporters who have already been activated. In addition, representatives from politics are also needed at this point, who can support the OSF in the various projects.

Goals of the communication approach

Following the findings from chapter 2, the communication concept focuses on the goals of attention and awareness for the topic/problem and the associated approach of the Open Search Foundation. The first goal is to increase attention and thus awareness of the Open Search Foundation in order to increase the basis for future fundraising activities.

For the main target group of "*recipients/users*", the aim is also to enhance digital skills in dealing with Internet search and search engines – or in other words: increase search literacy.

Example of a work package for the main target group "*recipients/users*"

As described, the financial resources of a start-up are usually limited. This is also the case with the Open Search Foundation. For this reason, the work packages identified concentrate on elements that can be driven primarily by the

contributions of the volunteer supporters. Various communication media serve as a basis, the design of which can be operated independently of third-party institutions. These include the website <https://opensearchfoundation.org>, newsletters, podcasts and social media marketing. In particular in the beginning the main actors of the OSF use their personal accounts to increase attention (above all via Business networks such as LinkedIn) and the already existing expert networks, which are to be developed further.

In addition, a so-called toolbox was developed with measures aimed at making the topic accessible to a broad population in a simple, entertaining way. These "Awareness Campaigns and Concepts to Promote Search Literacy in Europe" use checklists, handbooks, interactive learning games and infographics for roadshows and classic online/offline communication as well as didactic packages for use in schools. TED Talk-like videos are also used to achieve a kind of viral effect (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Work packages for the main target group "users"
[Source: 24].

4 Short outlook

Many people who hear about the OSF project are astonished, shocked, or just laugh. They say: "If Microsoft can't beat Google with Bing, how are you going to do it?" or "Why should this work now?" The answer: OSF has an idea that is promising. This is also the feedback when the technical approach has been presented in various places. In addition, at least on the side of politics and business - also due to the experience of the Covid-19 pandemic, when it was noticed that certain resources (such as medicines) were no longer in the direct access of the EU - the realization is growing that Europe must also make itself more independent of other states an dominating players in the digital sphere. This is especially true for one of the most important resources currently available: Information.

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